

Enhancing 'national transformation capacity' for Vietnam to accelerate its growth.

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(PLO) - The 10% growth target is a significant challenge, forcing us to consider institutional reform and "unleashing" private enterprises as vital breakthroughs to realize our aspirations for growth in the new era.

The 14th National Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam set the mission of transforming Vietnam into a high-income country, but the pressure to maintain double-digit growth is considerable given the decline of traditional drivers such as capital and cheap labor. So how can we activate new energy sources?

Speaking to the *Ho Chi Minh City Law* Newspaper, Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien, an economic expert, affirmed that only major institutional overhauls are powerful enough to turn this aspiration into reality.

Transforming the growth model and fostering private sector dynamism.

Reporter : *Sir, Vietnam aims for GDP growth exceeding 10% in the coming period. How do you assess the feasibility of this goal when traditional drivers such as capital, resources, and cheap labor are gradually reaching their limits ?*

+ Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien : If we continue operating with the old momentum, achieving double-digit growth will be very difficult and carries inherent risks regarding quality. Traditional drivers - capital, resources, cheap labor - have reached their limits, only sufficient to maintain short-term momentum but unable to create the impetus for sustainable development.

To achieve a growth rate exceeding 10%, Vietnam must restructure its economy and create new opportunities instead of merely making piecemeal policy adjustments. The focus should be on a drastic shift from extensive to intensive growth: using productivity and innovation as benchmarks. Vietnamese businesses must truly master technology to penetrate deep into the value chain, rather than simply engaging in outsourcing.

The key strategy is to upgrade Ho Chi Minh City and Hanoi into global cities – the hubs of multinational corporations. Simultaneously, there is a need for strong development of free

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Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien.

trade zones, the aviation economy centered around Long Thanh International Airport, and digital and green economic ecosystems.

Ultimately, breakthrough growth doesn't come from expectations, but depends on "national transformation capacity." This is the ability to absorb capital and technology from integration and transform them into endogenous capacity and real competitiveness. Only by solving this

problem can Vietnam escape the middle-income trap and enter a new trajectory of prosperity.

Vietnamese businesses need to master technology and embrace green transformation to escape the role of mere outsourcing, participate deeply in global value chains, and realize their aspirations for prosperity. (Photo: QH)

The documents of the 14th Party Congress identify the private sector as the most important driving force. This is a major step forward in thinking. However, to reassure entrepreneurs that they can invest large sums of capital for the long term instead of engaging in short-term

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speculation, what specific breakthroughs are needed regarding property rights protection and legal security?

To create momentum for breakthrough growth, Vietnam must activate new driving forces, in which the private sector plays a particularly important role. Only when entrepreneurs dare to think big, are independent and innovative, will the economy truly become self-reliant.

When institutions truly protect property rights, reduce risks for producers, and eliminate the benefits of speculation, the private sector will become the central driving force, propelling the economy towards self-reliance and prosperity.

Therefore, the business system needs consistency: protecting property rights and ensuring equal access to resources. When opportunities are not distorted by the "request-and-grant" mechanism, businesses will abandon the "short-term trading" mindset and confidently invest for the long term.

Simultaneously, the State needs to create an interconnected ecosystem (private sector - State - FDI) to accumulate endogenous capacity. The principles for coordinating capital flows must be clear: Production costs must be lower than speculation costs; conditional incentives should be given to production, while strict penalties should be imposed on speculation.

In terms of finance, monetary policy needs to genuinely channel capital into the economy. A national investment stimulus program should be implemented, in which preferential interest rates act as "seed capital" to encourage the private sector to boldly expand its operations.

In particular, transparency in the business environment is a prerequisite. We must resolutely reduce the informal sector and the problem of counterfeit goods – areas that stifle innovation. A market where legitimate businesses bear high compliance costs while fraud is tolerated will never have large enterprises.

Mastering core technologies and the challenges of green transformation.

To achieve high income by 2045, we cannot continue with low-value manufacturing. According to him, how should economic policies be redesigned to force Vietnamese businesses to absorb and master technology, instead of just providing incentives for FDI as before?

To realize its aspiration of high income by 2045, Vietnam must break away from the low-

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constraint": high logistics and compliance costs, low total factor productivity (TFP), and weak ability to compete in international markets. Without comprehensive solutions, all technological advancements will remain localized.

Businesses that do not meet green standards will find it difficult to get their products into major markets.

Photo: QH

Therefore, economic policy needs to be restructured according to an integrated growth model, where technological upgrades are closely linked to infrastructure and institutional reforms. Instead of offering incentives, the focus should shift to setting conditions, so that FDI and domestic enterprises can accumulate production capacity together.

Firstly, shift FDI incentives from input-based to output-based (localization rate, R&D, human resource quality). The mechanism must be flexible: only those meeting targets will receive incentives, forcing FDI to link its benefits to upgrading domestic capabilities.

Secondly, the government needs to design a specific upgrade roadmap for each industry. Through technical standards and public procurement regulations, policies must create pressure for Vietnamese businesses to "learn and grow" in order to participate in the market, thereby increasing their competitiveness.

Third, consider reducing logistics costs and compliance as core industrial policies. Developing infrastructure and digitizing procedures will directly increase TFP and open

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Fourth, develop a national supplier ecosystem. Technical support and supply chain connectivity programs are needed to help Vietnamese businesses move out of low-level processing positions and climb to higher value chains.

Ultimately, fiscal and monetary capital flows must be redirected towards technology, automation, and R&D. National resources should prioritize quality upgrades over mere expansion.

For the first time, environmental protection is placed at the center, on par with the economy. How can we address the challenge of balancing the high costs of green transition with the declining capital accumulation needs of businesses after the crisis?

Placing environmental protection on par with economic development is a major step forward in development thinking. It is important to recognize that green standards are not local barriers but common benchmarks towards global sustainable development, reflecting international commitments on climate, environment, and [social](#) responsibility .

In this context, businesses that do not meet green standards will find it increasingly difficult, if not impossible, to get their goods into major markets, regardless of how cheap the price or how high the production volume.

However, the challenge lies in the fact that many Vietnamese businesses are weakened after the crisis, have limited capital accumulation, while the cost of green transition is high. Therefore, the question is not about choosing green or growth, but about green transition in a way

Shift from a managerial mindset to a creative and transformative one.

The crucial mindset for decisive action right now is to shift from a managerial mindset to one of creation and transformation. The strategy is in place, and opportunities are rapidly emerging; if the system continues to operate with the inertia of control, defense, and avoidance of responsibility, these opportunities will slip away before they can materialize.

In particular, it is necessary to correctly understand the role of Party resolutions. These strategic orientations are only effective when they are promptly institutionalized into laws and specific procedures. The institutionalization process must be fast and practical; delays here will slow down the process of producing results.

Government agencies at all levels need to act based on competence and results, not form. Every policy must address bottlenecks, create new capabilities, and be measurable; otherwise, it needs immediate

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that enhances capacity, rather than simply increasing compliance costs.

First and foremost, it is necessary to design a tiered green transformation roadmap that is appropriate to the size, industry, and financial capacity of each enterprise.

Secondly, the government needs to share the costs of green transition through green credit and interest rate subsidies, viewing this as an investment in upgrading production capacity to meet global standards rather than short-term incentives.

Third, green standards need to be transformed into a market advantage. Meeting green standards helps businesses maintain export markets, participate more deeply in global supply chains, and access stable orders.

Effective management requires decisive action based on legal frameworks and transparent data. Decisions must be swift, well-founded, and accountable. Simultaneously, there needs to be a shift from a plan-making mindset to a problem-solving one, with a willingness to adapt to practical realities.

Ultimately, every opportunity must be viewed as a transformative challenge to accumulate long-term capacity. Only with this mindset can new directions truly be implemented, creating genuine prosperity for the country.

Dr. **HUYNH THANH DIEN**

Decentralization is linked to responsibility and a new mindset for action.

The political report of the 14th Party Congress emphasized decentralization, delegation of power, and streamlining of the apparatus to remove bottlenecks in implementation. From an institutional perspective, how can this mechanism be legalized to protect local leaders who dare to make decisions and take action, avoiding the situation where issues are pushed up to the central government for fear of responsibility?

+ Promoting decentralization, delegation of power, and streamlining the administrative apparatus is the right direction, but the biggest bottleneck currently is not a lack of authority but a fear of responsibility. The main reason lies in the fact that the law is not yet clear enough and the data is not interconnected and integrated, leaving decision-makers without reliable information to be held accountable.

Therefore, the issue is not just about granting more power, but about legalizing decentralization coupled with mechanisms to protect those who make the right decisions. It is necessary to clearly define the boundaries between authority and responsibility,

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procedures, and based on what data systems, while the central government focuses on designing the framework and monitoring the results.

At the same time, legal protection must be provided for officials who dare to act for the common good, clearly distinguishing policy risks from legal violations; decisions made within the proper authority, following the correct procedures, and based on valid data must be protected, even if the results are not as expected. Along with this, there should be a shift from pre-auditing to post-auditing with discipline, empowering localities to take initiative but linking it to accountability based on results.

Ultimately, interconnected and transparent data plays a crucial role. When laws are clear, data is readily available, and accountability is fairly established, institutional trust is strengthened, and local leaders will dare to make decisions and take action for development goals.

Thank you, sir.

Institutional breakthroughs, repositioning domestic businesses.

Experts and business associations have frankly pointed out critical bottlenecks and proposed urgent solutions regarding institutions, capital flows, and high-quality human resources to turn aspirations into reality during this crucial period.

To achieve 10% growth, Vietnam needs to restructure its economy, consider the private sector as the core driving force, and shift its mindset towards development-oriented thinking. (Photo:

QH)

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A major economic overhaul using a three-pronged approach.

In my opinion, the double-digit growth target for the 2026-2030 period is not just an economic indicator, but a "survival imperative" for Vietnam to escape the middle-income trap before the aging population sets in. To realize this, the economy needs a comprehensive "surgery."

Firstly, institutional revolution must be the top priority to remove the root of all bottlenecks. Management thinking needs to shift strongly from control to creation, boldly cutting overlapping regulations. In particular, the immediate implementation of legislation to protect officials who dare to think and act must break the inertia of the public administration and unblock the flow of investment capital that is currently stalled.

Secondly, we need to restructure growth drivers based on leading companies and core technologies. We should learn from the Chaebol model or Taiwanese technology conglomerates to nurture national businesses capable of competing globally. Tax and credit policies must be redesigned to redirect capital from real estate speculation to industrial production, semiconductors, AI, and green energy, aiming for the digital economy to account for 30% of GDP.

Thirdly, breakthroughs in infrastructure and human resources are crucial. Besides the North-South high-speed railway project and energy security, the key lies in people. Vietnam needs a national-scale skills training strategy to prepare tens of thousands of high-quality engineers, ready to welcome the new generation of FDI.

This is a time or never for us to reposition our nation in the new era.

Dr. **Le Ba Chi Nhan** , *economic expert:*

Four fundamental conditions for 10% economic growth.

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To realize the 10% growth target envisioned by the 14th Party Congress, four fundamental conditions and sufficiently strong policy breakthroughs are needed.

Firstly, the growth model must shift from one based on capital and labor to one based on productivity, technology, and innovation. The main policy focus

should be on improving total factor productivity (TFP). Domestic enterprises must maintain a central position in the innovation ecosystem instead of merely engaging in outsourcing.

Secondly, view institutional breakthroughs as the "lever of levers." We need to shift our thinking from management to creation, substantially reducing compliance costs. Institutions must become a competitive advantage, not a barrier.

Thirdly, economic restructuring should focus on forming a strong force of national enterprises to lead the supply chain. The state-owned economy needs to redefine its pioneering role, focusing only on key sectors where the private sector has not yet been able to operate.

Fourth, consider human resource investment as the "soft infrastructure" that determines success or failure. Reforming the training of engineers and technology experts should be given equal priority to investing in hard infrastructure.

Ultimately, a flexible governance mechanism is needed, along with individualized accountability for leaders. The core issue is no longer "should we or shouldn't we," but rather daring to make drastic changes and implement substantive actions to realize the nation's aspiration for development and high income.

Mr. **NGUYEN NGOC HOA** , *Chairman of the Ho Chi Minh City Business Association (HUBA)*:

Creating a favorable environment for Ho Chi Minh City's growth.

2026 is a golden opportunity for Ho Chi Minh City to make a breakthrough, but it requires absolute stability in its operational mechanisms. However, in the context of reorganizing administrative units according to a two-tiered government model and the pressure for green transformation, businesses need a solid policy foundation. To

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reassure the business community and encourage them to focus their efforts, the association proposes five key solutions.

Firstly, ensure policy continuity. The process of streamlining the organizational structure requires a clear and consistent legal framework. Under no circumstances should adjustments to mechanisms or personnel arrangements disrupt the flow of production and business.

Secondly, it's necessary to remove procedural bottlenecks. Clearly identify the responsible parties to definitively resolve outstanding issues related to taxes, land, and investment. Simplifying procedures in the digital environment must be substantive, aiming to minimize compliance costs for businesses.

Thirdly, elevate the dialogue and role of associations. The government needs to maintain regular dialogue channels, viewing businesses as partners in policy critique. At the same time, it needs to create conditions for associations to innovate their models and effectively support businesses in digital transformation and green transformation – essential "passports" for venturing into the global market.

Mr. **VU DANG KHUE** , *Chairman of the Binh Duong Small and Medium Enterprises Association:*

Removing capital barriers and fostering substantive regional linkages.

To realize the aspiration of becoming a developed, high-income country set forth at the 14th Party Congress, the economy needs leaps and bounds rather than gradual progress.

From the perspective of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), the focus of this transformation must begin with a complete shift in the position of domestic businesses. The economy cannot continue to rely on outsourcing or foreign direct investment (FDI). Instead, the government needs to create

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economy will no longer be an option but a vital imperative for breakthroughs in productivity.

Alongside elevating its status, the capital bottleneck needs to be addressed through unconventional financial thinking. Instead of relying on collateral, capital should be channeled through credit-based guarantee funds and real cash flow. A testing mechanism (sandbox) also needs to be implemented soon to protect innovative business models from outdated legal barriers.

In particular, regional linkages between Ho Chi Minh City and neighboring provinces and cities must be more substantive, becoming a "laboratory" for superior policies and synchronized logistics infrastructure.

QUANG HUY *wrote*

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